

THE INFLUENCE OF THE REMUNERATION SYSTEM AND WORK MOTIVATION ON PERFORMANCE THROUGH JOB SATISFACTION IN NURSES AT SYECH YUSUF HOSPITAL, GOWA DISTRICT

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Abstract

Success in motivating nurses and providing adequate rewards can influence their level of job satisfaction, which in turn has the potential to influence their performance in providing health services. This study aims to investigate the influence of the remuneration system and work motivation on nurse performance through the level of job satisfaction at the Syech Yusuf Regional General Hospital (RSUD). The research method used is a quantitative approach with a *cross-sectional approach* study and data collection using a questionnaire distributed to nurses who work at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital. The sample for this study was 116 people. The research results show that a fair remuneration system and high work motivation have a positive impact on the level of job satisfaction of nurses. It was also found that the level of job satisfaction of nurses significantly influences their performance directly. Meanwhile, the results of the indirect analysis show that the results of the research show that there is an indirect influence of the remuneration system on performance through the satisfaction variable, with a significance value of 0.023 and the research findings also show that there is an indirect influence of work motivation on performance through the satisfaction variable, with a significance value of 0.025. Therefore, hospital management is advised to pay attention to a fair remuneration system and effective work motivation strategies to increase nurses' job satisfaction, which in turn will support increasing their performance in providing quality health services at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital.

Keywords: Remuneration, Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Performance, and Hospital Nurses.

INTRODUCTION

Nurses are one of the most important medical personnel in hospitals, because their duties include patient care, administering medication, monitoring the patient's condition, and coordinating with doctors and other medical personnel. The performance of nurses in hospitals is very important because it can influence the quality of services provided to patients and their families. Nursing services are provided in the form of nurse performance, and must be based on high thinking or ability to do it so that performance can support implementation in nursing service duties (Hasanah & Nuringwahyu, 2020).

Nurses have an important function in serving patient health, because nurses are around patients 24 hours a day and are responsible for patient health services. The number of nurses is greater than other staff, almost more than 50% of employees in hospitals are nurses, so nurses are needed who are able to work productively and are satisfied with their performance. As well as being involved with their work so they can continue working optimally even for long periods of time (Harfika, 2017).

Nurse performance can also affect a hospital's reputation, patient satisfaction, and the success of patient treatment and recovery. Therefore, hospital management needs to pay attention to factors that can influence nurse performance, such as the remuneration system, work motivation and job satisfaction (Hadi, 2019).

The results of the performance evaluation of nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital using nursing care standards based on the 2010 PPNI standards are as follows:

Table 1: Achievement of Nurse Performance Levels at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital Based on PPNI Standards. Year 2022

No	Nursing Care Indicators	Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital	Standard
1	Nursing Assessment	84%	100%
2	Nursing diagnoses	80%	
3	Nursing planning	78.01%	
4	Nursing actions	75.22%	
5	Nursing Evaluation	70%	
Average		78%	

Source: Monitoring and Evaluation Data at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital, 2022

From the results of the table above, it is found that in 2022 the performance level of nurses in the inpatient installation of Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital will be an average of 78%, so it can be concluded that the performance of nurses in the inpatient installation of Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital is not in accordance with the PPNI standard achievement (100%).

Based on the results of interviews with several nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital, it was stated that Nurses lack enthusiasm for their work and always feel tired quickly because there is too much work must be completed. This was indicated by several nurses who always arriving late, this is due to a lack of work motivation among nurses . Some nurses also stated that they feel less satisfied with their work because of them feel that what they are doing is not in accordance with what is expected obtained. The data on job satisfaction for nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital is 73.2 % for 2020 .

The importance of research on the influence of remuneration systems and work motivation on performance through job satisfaction in nurses according to researchers can be seen from the following things:

1. The relationship between remuneration, motivation, job satisfaction and performance: Remuneration and work motivation have a big influence on job satisfaction and performance of nurses. Therefore, it is important to know how these two factors influence each other and influence nurse performance.
2. Relevance to the quality of health services: The performance of nurses greatly influences the quality of health services provided to patients. Therefore, it is important to know what influences nurse performance so that the quality of health services can be improved.
3. The need for increased motivation and performance of nurses: Good performance of nurses is essential to ensure good quality health services. Therefore, it is important to know what can motivate nurses and improve their performance.
4. Limited resources: The resources available in the health sector are very limited, so it is important to ensure that existing resources are used effectively and efficiently. Research on the influence of remuneration systems and work motivation on performance through job satisfaction in nurses can help in achieving this.

5. The importance of understanding the conditions and dynamics of the health industry: The health industry is very complex and developing quickly. Therefore, it is important to understand the dynamics and conditions of this industry in order to ensure that health services can be provided well.

So based on the information above, the author is interested in conducting research on the influence of the remuneration system and work motivation on performance through job satisfaction among nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

Nurse performance is a nurse's activity in implementing as well as possible his authority, duties and responsibilities in order to achieve the goals of the main duties of the profession and the realization of the goals and objectives of the organizational unit. Nurse performance is actually the same as work performance in the company. Nurses want their performance to be measured based on objective standards that are open and communicable. If nurses are cared for and appreciated with superior respect, they will be more motivated to achieve higher levels of achievement (Hasibuan, 2003).

Performance appraisal is needed to determine the level of individual contribution to the organization. The objectives of performance appraisal in general can be divided into two, namely:

1. Provide *rewards* for previous performance.
2. Motivate performance improvements in the future.

All information obtained from performance appraisals can be used to manage human resources to be more efficient in achieving organizational goals. Apart from that, organizations also adapt to design plans that aim to improve employee performance, such as providing employee training and development, as well as more suitable work placements (Hasanah et al, 2020).

Remuneration

Application Remuneration system for Managing Officers, Board BLU Supervisors and Employees are intended so that all hospital *stakeholders can improve their respective professionalism and performance which in the end can improve the performance of hospital services.*

The aim of implementing the remuneration system is to stimulate employee motivation to have high commitment to work by complying with all applicable rules and regulations, building a solid work team, demonstrating the performance expected by the hospital and spurring employee motivation to build hospital competency on an ongoing basis (Hoboubi , 2017).

Work motivation

Motivation is an impulse that arises from within a person which will direct a person's actions with the aim of achieving a desired result. Motivation is important because motivation is what causes, channels and supports human behavior so that they are willing to work hard and enthusiastically achieve optimal results.

According to Siagian (2003) defines motivation as a driving force that causes someone to be willing and willing to mobilize their abilities in the form of expertise or skills, energy or time to carry out various activities for which they are responsible and fulfill their obligations in order to achieve the goals of various targets that have been set. Previously determined. Motivation is a state in a person's personality that drives the individual's desire to carry out certain activities to achieve a goal.

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is defined by Robbins as an individual's general attitude towards his work. Work requires interaction with co-workers and superiors, following organizational rules and policies, meeting performance standards, living in working conditions that are often less than ideal, and other similar things. This means that an employee's assessment of whether he is satisfied or dissatisfied with his job is a complex summation of a number of discrete job elements (differentiated and separated from each other). That job satisfaction is the level of pleasant feelings obtained from assessing someone's work or experience. Work (Kader et al, 2021).

Conceptual framework

MATERIALS METHODS

Research design

This research uses an analytical observational research approach, with a *cross-sectional approach* study or cross section, namely research variables are measured or collected at one time

Location and Research Plans

The research location is Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital

Populations and Samples

The population in this study were all nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital. The number of samples in this study was 116 respondents .

Data Collection Methods

Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire created by researchers referring to the conceptual framework and variables to be studied for respondents. Researchers will provide a questionnaire in the form of a Google form questionnaire which will be filled out by nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital which consists of 4 questionnaire items, namely performance, work motivation, remuneration satisfaction and job satisfaction.

Data Analysis Methods

In this research, data analysis was carried out after the data from the questionnaire was collected and then re-checked to determine the completeness of the content. After the complete data was collected and tabulated based on the sub-variables studied, then calculations were carried out using the SPSS program using path analysis. Path analysis aims to determine the direct or indirect influence of exogenous (independent) variables on endogenous (dependent) variables with significance ($\text{Sigma F} < 0.05$) and significance ($\text{Sigma T} < 0.05$).

RESULT

General Characteristics of Respondents

Based on table 1, in the age category it is known that the majority of respondents are in the 30 - 39 year age category, namely 60 people (51.7%). Meanwhile, the fewest age characteristics were 50 – 59 years old, 9 people (7.8%). Based on gender, the majority of respondents were women, namely 89 people (76.7%). Meanwhile, the number of male respondents was 27 people (23.3%).

Based on educational characteristics, the majority of respondents had a professional educational background as a nurse with a total of 69 people (59.5%). Meanwhile, the fewest respondents had a Master's degree in Nursing, namely 2 people (1.7%). Based on length of service, the majority of respondents worked for less than 10 years, namely 61 people (52.6%). Meanwhile, there were 55 respondents who had worked for more than 10 years (47.4%). Based on marital status, the majority of respondents were married, namely 96 people (82.8%). Meanwhile, respondents with unmarried status were 20 people (17.2%).

Bivariate Analysis

The results of the bivariate analysis will see the relationship between the independent variables one by one and the dependent variable. So in this research we can see the relationship between the variables remuneration, satisfaction, motivation and performance.

Based on table 2 , it was found that respondents were in the variables remuneration in the satisfied category and stated that their performance was good, there were 66 people (98.5%). And respondents in the dissatisfied category and stated that their performance was good were 49 people (100.0%). $p \text{ value} = 1.000$ then the $p\text{-value}$ is > 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is no significant relationship with remuneration with performance. On variables satisfaction in the high category and stated good performance as many as 113 people (99.1%). And respondents in the low category stated that their performance was good as many as 2 people (100.0%). $p \text{ value} = 1.000$ then the $p\text{-value}$ is > 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is no significant

relationship between satisfaction and performance. On variables motivation in the high category and declared good performance as many as 112 people (99.1%). And respondents in the low category stated that their performance was good as many as 3 people (100.0%). p value = 1.000, then the p -value is > 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is no significant relationship between motivation and performance).

Multivariate Analysis

Based on the results of the analysis in table 3, it was found that the p value for the remuneration and motivation variables was found to be 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was accepted (H1) and it could be concluded that the remuneration variable had a positive and significant effect on the motivation of nurses at Syech Regional Hospital. Joseph. The results of the analysis of the remuneration variable on satisfaction were 0.001 ($p < 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was accepted (H2) and it could be concluded that the remuneration variable had a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction for nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital.

The results of the analysis of the motivation variable on satisfaction showed that the p value was 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was accepted (H3) and it could be concluded that the motivation variable had a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction for nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital. The results of the analysis of the satisfaction variable on performance were 0.458 ($p > 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was rejected (H4) and it could be concluded that the satisfaction variable had no positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at Syech Yusuf Hospital. The results of the analysis of the motivation variable on performance were 0.753 ($p > 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was rejected (H5) and it could be concluded that the motivation variable had no positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at Syech Yusuf Hospital.

The results of the analysis of the remuneration variable on performance were 0.962 ($p > 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was rejected (H6) and it could be concluded that the remuneration variable had no positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital. Apart from using more than one independent variable, this research also uses intervening variables. Intervening variables are mediating variables whose function is to mediate the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. To test intervening variables, the following path analysis method is used:

Figure 2: Path Analysis of Research Variables

Based on the picture above, it shows the influence of the independent variables and intervening variables on the dependent variable, both directly, indirectly and in total.

DISCUSSION

The direct influence of the remuneration system on the motivation of nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital

Based on the research results, it was found that the p value for the remuneration variable on motivation was 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was accepted (H3) and it could be concluded that the remuneration variable had a positive and significant direct effect on work motivation for nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital.

The fact that remuneration variables influence motivation, and through motivational pathways, impact nurse performance, provides a more comprehensive view of how these elements interact in the hospital context. This shows that efforts to design and implement a fair and encouraging remuneration system can have an impact far beyond simply providing financial compensation (Hadi, et al. 2019).

In Syech Yusuf Hospital or other health care environments, where nurses have high work demands and work under pressure, having strong motivation can make a significant difference in the quality of service provided to patients. If remuneration variables are able to form higher motivation among nurses, this will stimulate efforts to provide better care, improve team coordination, and increase the overall effectiveness of the hospital (Nabawi, 2019).

The direct influence of the remuneration system on satisfaction with nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital

Based on the research results, there is a direct influence of the remuneration variable on satisfaction of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$), so the hypothesis is accepted (H2) and it can be concluded that the remuneration variable has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction for nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital.

The results of testing the influence of remuneration system variables on job satisfaction show a path coefficient value of 0.050 with a t value of 29.100. This value is greater than the t table (1.960). These results mean that the remuneration system has an effect on nurses' job satisfaction by 145.5%.

According to Suearmanto (2009) , the concept of remuneration refers to providing rewards to employees as a form of recognition for the contributions they make to the organization where they work. Remuneration has a significant positive impact on employee job satisfaction levels. This indicates that the feelings of satisfaction and pleasure that employees get from a fair and adequate compensation system can influence their motivation and productivity in carrying out their daily tasks (Herlinda, 2016) .

Direct influence of motivation on satisfaction of nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital

Based on the research results that there is a direct influence of the motivation variable on satisfaction, it was found that the p value was 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was accepted (H3) and it can be concluded that the motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction for nurses at Syech Regional Hospital. Joseph.

This is in line with research by Mujianto et al, 2023. Which states that the results of hypothesis testing using Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis have proven that there is a positive and significant influence between work motivation and the level of job satisfaction in the context of doctors. These results indicate that the higher the level of work motivation of doctors, the higher the level of job satisfaction they feel.

This phenomenon can be explained by several aspects. First, the nursing profession has a strong ethical dimension, where nurses take an oath to help and care for patients who need medical care. In this context, nurses' work motivation is not only driven by economic factors, but also by their calling and desire to provide benefits to others. In the view of many doctors, medical service to patients is a form of charity, which is expected to receive appreciation and reward from God. Second, intrinsic motivation obtained from health services that are oriented towards caring for patients can influence nurses' job satisfaction. The sense of satisfaction they get from helping patients heal or restore their health is the main source of their job satisfaction (Seema et al, 2021).

The direct influence of satisfaction on the performance of nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital

The results of the study showed that job satisfaction did not have a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital. This is in line with the research results of Azhari, Resmawan, & Ikhsan (2021) which stated that job satisfaction does not have a significant effect on employee performance. Other research conducted by Nabawi (2019) also showed similar results where job satisfaction did not have a significant effect on employee performance due to the high constant value (a value) and low job satisfaction coefficient value (X).

The results of research from Mira et al. (2019) proves that job satisfaction has a positive relationship, but the relationship is not very strong. Job satisfaction influences employee performance by 1.5%, while other factors not examined in this research have an influence of 98.5%. An employee's job satisfaction really depends on things related to their work (Seema et al., 2021). Employees will get job satisfaction if there is stability and stability in their work, both in their career and the world of work (Kader et al., 2021).

Working conditions can have a negative impact on job satisfaction. This can take the form of a decline in the physical and spiritual health of employees (Hoboubi et al., 2017). For example, there has been a decline in job satisfaction due to heavy workloads occurring in one organization in China (Wu et al., 2018).

Mangole et al (2015) stated that nurses will be required to provide the best performance because their performance will be directly felt by patients. A nurse's performance shows the magnitude of the contribution made to the hospital where she works, as well as reflecting the performance of a hospital because patients will often have direct contact with nurses.

The direct influence of motivation on performance among nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital.

The research results showed that work motivation had no direct positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital with a p value of 0.753 (>0.05). However, motivation influences performance through job satisfaction.

In this case, there is an indirect influence of motivation on performance. However, motivation does not have a direct effect on performance.

Motivation does not always have a direct influence on performance, highlighting the complexity of the interactions between factors that influence both. This is because each individual has different styles and levels of motivation as well as personality factors that can play a role in the extent to which motivation can have an impact on performance. The professionalism of a nurse's work cannot be separated from the drive or enthusiasm within herself or the environment in which she works (Marquis & Moustou, 2010 in Naibaho, 2014).

Performance is the result of a variety of variables, including technical ability, knowledge, interpersonal skills, work environment, and external factors that are not necessarily related to a person's level of motivation. Although motivation can trigger enthusiasm and energy to carry out tasks, the quality and effectiveness of carrying out these tasks can be influenced by various other, more complex factors.

The direct influence of the remuneration system on the performance of nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital

Based on the results of the analysis of the remuneration and performance variables, it was found that the p value was 0.962 ($p > 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was rejected (H1) and it could be concluded that the direct variable remuneration had no positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital.

According to (Hasibuan and Melayu, 2013), the level of employee job satisfaction is influenced by a number of factors. These factors include providing fair and appropriate rewards, placement in positions that match skills, appropriate workload, working conditions and environment, availability of equipment that supports work, risks associated with work, career development opportunities, and attitude and style. Leadership from superiors.

These results are in line with research conducted by Mazura (2012) showing that there is no positive influence between incentive variables and performance variables with a significant value α ($p \text{ value} > \alpha$), namely $\alpha = 1.007$ where p is greater than α ($1.007 > 0.05$). This is because there are differences in indicators for measuring a person's performance. So the results obtained are also different.

Findings from research conducted by Soetisna in 2015 showed that remuneration had no influence on staff performance. Even though staff complained about the implementation of remuneration not being in line with their expectations, surprisingly, the performance of both individuals and units quantitatively always improved after the remuneration system was implemented.

Indirect influence of work motivation on performance through job satisfaction among nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital

The research results show that the work motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction for nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital with a p value of 0.025 (< 0.05). Motivation is a process that determines how much effort will be devoted to carrying out work (Buhler, 2004). High motivation can strengthen nurses' commitment to the hospital or health facility where they work. Motivation allows nurses to be loyal to their profession and institution, build strong relationships with patients and colleagues, and contribute continuously to the

care team. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Suryawan and Andrew (2013) which states that there is empirical evidence that motivation influences job satisfaction with a high level of significance, namely 0.000. Job satisfaction is a form of self-esteem that each individual obtains after the individual works in accordance with organizational goals.

Other research that is in line with the results of this research is research conducted by Mubaroqah and Yusuf (2020) which states that work motivation has a positive and significant influence on employee job satisfaction. Juniari, Riana, and Subudi (2015) in their research also stated that work motivation has a positive and significant influence on employee job satisfaction.

Indirect influence of the remuneration system on performance through job satisfaction among nurses at Syech Yusuf Gowa Regional Hospital

The results of the research show that the remuneration variable has an indirect effect on the performance variable through the job satisfaction variable. It was found that the p value was 0.023 ($p < 0.05$) so that the hypothesis was accepted (H2) and it could be concluded that the remuneration variable had a direct positive and significant effect on performance. Through job satisfaction for nurses at Syech Yusuf Regional Hospital.

The results of in-depth interviews indicated that a number of informants believed that remuneration had a limited impact on the level of job satisfaction. Several respondents stated that the lack of satisfaction among them was caused by lack of clarity in the remuneration calculation system. Weaknesses in the explanation of how the remuneration system is calculated affect the level of satisfaction of some doctors and medical personnel with this system.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, there is an indirect effect of remuneration on performance through the satisfaction variable with a significance value of 0.023. Based on the research results, there is an indirect effect of motivation on performance through the satisfaction variable with a significance value of 0.025. For the remuneration system, management can consider periodic salary increases for employees or providing bonuses or incentives so that they can motivate employees to work responsibly, continue to develop themselves, and contribute more to the progress of the organization.

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